

RISK FACTORS AND DIAGNOSIS OF KIDNEY STONE**Bahromov Bekzod Shavkatovich**

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Abstract. *Kidney stone affect 15-18% of the population in industrialized countries. The average life time risk of stone formation has been reported in the range of 7-13%. Recurrent stone formation is a common part of the medical care of patients with stone diseases. The aetiology of this disorder is multi factorial and is strongly related to dietary lifestyle habits or practices. Increased rates of hypertension, diabetes and obesity which are linked to nephrolithiasis, also contribute to an increase in stone formation. Hence, this study was undertaken to find out the prevalence among kidney stone patients. Also to find out the risk factors influencing the development of kidney stones especially Family history, inadequate fluid intake, Stress, Over weight and Obesity, Dietary habits and lifestyle modifications, association with other diseases (diabetes, hypertension).*

Keywords: *Kidney stone, risk factors.*

INTRODUCTION

Kidney stones, one of the most painful of the urologic disorders, are not a product of modern life. Unfortunately, kidney stones are one of the most common disorders of the urinary tract. A large number of people are suffering from urinary stone problem all over the globe. Kidney stones, which are solid crystals that form from dissolved minerals in urine, can be caused by both environmental and metabolic problems. Calcium oxalate and/or phosphate stones account for almost 80% of all renal stones observed in economically developed countries. Kidney stones are quite common and usually affect people who are between 35 and 65 years of age. They affect men more than women. It is estimated that renal colic (severe pain caused by a kidney stone) affects about 13-25% of men, and 5-8% of women. In India, 15% of the population is expected to have urinary stones, out of which 65% may end up with loss of kidneys or renal damage. Recurrent stone formation is a common problem with all types of stones and therefore an important part of the medical care of patients with stone disease.

In most countries with a relatively high incidence of renal calculi due to climate, diet habits, local geology with hydro mineralogy and sanitation by affecting geo mineralogy. Rising global temperatures could lead to an increase in kidney stones. Dehydration has been linked to stone disease, particularly in warmer climates, and global warming will exacerbate this effect. The correlation between increased environmental temperature and increased number of stone events supports the conclusion that global warming has an impact on the development of stones. As a result, the prevalence of stone disease may increase, along with the costs of treating the condition. The researchers discovered that stone formers had a 65% greater risk of developing chronic kidney disease (CKD) and a 45% increased risk of developing end-stage renal disease (ESRD), the most severe form of CKD.

Diet may have a significant impact on the incidence of urinary stones. The incidence has been steadily increasing, paralleling the rise in other diseases associated with the so called 'Western diet'. Being obese (higher BMI) and experiencing weight gain have been associated with stone risk among men and women. Diet and fluid intake may be important factors in the development of urinary stones. As per capita income increases, the average diet changes, with an increase in saturated and unsaturated fatty acid; an increase in animal protein and sugar; and a

decrease in dietary fibre, vegetable protein and unrefined carbohydrates. Increased animal protein intake, lower potassium intake, lower fluid intake were recently identified to higher stone risk.

Clinical diagnosis of ureteric colic

Ureteric colic is classically among the most painful of emergency presentations. Typically, pain of varying intensity is felt in the flank and radiates towards the groin. When the stone is lodged distally in the ureter (ureterovesical junction), there is no flank pain. Low-grade or intermittent flank pain can occur with stones in the renal pelvis. However, flank pain is not a specific symptom of ureteric calculi. In patients with acute flank pain referred for UHCT, ureteric stones are found in 38–75% of examinations. The presence or absence of haematuria is not sufficiently sensitive or specific for the diagnosis of ureteric calculi. In 250 patients with flank pain, kidney stones on UHCT and concurrent urine testing, the sensitivity of haematuria for kidney stones was 91% and specificity %32. Of patients with flank pain but no haematuria, 24% had a stone. Eight of 20 with proven non-renal abdominal pain had haematuria. In a prospective study of 300 patients with acute flank pain, UHCT and concurrent urine testing, haematuria had a positive predictive value (PPV) of 65%, negative predictive value (NPV) of 75% and accuracy of 65% in predicting stone disease. In a retrospective review of UHCT, reports of 1000 patients with acute flank pain and concurrent urine microscopy, haematuria had a sensitivity of 87%, specificity of 51%, PPV of 75% and NPV of 68% for the presence of kidney stones. Fever suggests either a separate diagnosis of urinary tract infection or coexisting urinary tract infection.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we could establish a significant relationship between family history, diet and life style modifications, low fluid intake, obesity are the major factors play a role in development of renal calculi. We also found a significant relationship between patients associated with diabetes mellitus, hypertension and renal calculi. Life style changes helps to reduce recurrent stone disease. Renal calculi can be prevented by the most important thing is to drink plenty of water daily the goal should be to urinate from two to four litters per day make sure you avoided getting dehydrated, there are no specific dietary recommendation until a stone from your system has been analysed. After analysis diet can be evaluated and changes recommended.

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